

THE INTERNATIONAL RESEARCH GROUP ON WOOD PROTECTION

Section 5

Sustainability and Environment

The InnovaWood Module Bank: Building an international e-learning platform for shared MSc courses in wood science and technology

Mark Irle¹, Uwe Kies², Holger Militz³, Philipp Sauerbier³, Malvina Vieux¹,
Almin Prosic⁴, Benjamin Wolfsberger⁴, Frédéric Pichelin⁴, Ingo Mayer⁴

¹ Ecole Supérieure de Bois, BP 10605, rue Christian Pauc, 44306 Nantes, France,
mark.irle@ecoledubois.fr, malvina.vieux@ecoledubois.fr

² InnovaWood, 66 Rue de Luxembourg, 1000 Brussels, Belgium, uwe.kies@innovawood.com

³ University of Göttingen, Wood Biology and Wood Products, Büsgenweg 4, 37077 Göttingen, Germany,
hmilitz@gwdg.de, psauerb@gwdg.de

⁴ Berner Fachhochschule, Solothurnstrasse 102, 2504 Biel, Switzerland,
almin.prosic@bfh.ch, benjamin.wolfsberger@bfh.ch, frederic.pichelin@bfh.ch

Disclaimer

The opinions expressed in this document are those of the author(s) and are not necessarily the opinions or policy of the IRG Organization.

IRG SECRETARIAT
Box 5604
SE-114 86 Stockholm
Sweden
www.irg-wp.com

The InnovaWood Module Bank: Building an international e-learning platform for shared MSc courses in wood science and technology

Mark Irle¹, Uwe Kies², Holger Militz³, Philipp Sauerbier³, Malvina Vieux¹,
Almin Prosic⁴, Benjamin Wolfsberger⁴, Frédéric Pichelin⁴, Ingo Mayer⁴

¹ Ecole Supérieure de Bois, BP 10605, rue Christian Pauc, 44306 Nantes, France,
mark.irle@ecoledubois.fr, malvina.vieux@ecoledubois.fr

² InnovaWood, 66 Rue de Luxembourg, 1000 Brussels, Belgium, uwe.kies@innovawood.com

³ University of Göttingen, Wood Biology and Wood Products, Büsgenweg 4, 37077 Göttingen, Germany,
hmilitz@gwdg.de, psauerb@gwdg.de

⁴ Berner Fachhochschule, Solothurnstrasse 102, 2504 Biel, Switzerland,
almin.prosic@bfh.ch, benjamin.wolfsberger@bfh.ch, frederic.pichelin@bfh.ch

ABSTRACT

The InnovaWood Module Bank is a shared e-Learning platform for standalone science, technology and education modules in wood science. A group of members of InnovaWood have committed to jointly develop this platform. The institutes benefit in that they can widen the range of courses they offer and use their teaching capacities more efficiently. Students obtain the possibility to take online courses at another university without the need of costly exchange programmes. New e-Learning tools and teaching methods give them more choice and more flexibility to pursue their own individual preferences during their studies. To participate in the Module Bank, organisations must commit to providing at least one module of 3 ECTS at the MSc level. In return they obtain access to the whole series of modules that are offered collectively. The main benefits are that an institution obtains access to high quality lectures of experienced teachers in specific thematic fields and the opportunity to complement their core study programmes with additional online modules. Among others, these contain a module on ‘Wood degradation and wood protection’ by the University of Göttingen, which is relevant for IRG. The Module Bank contributes to new internationalisation experiences and a diversification of teaching contents and formats.

Keywords: e-Learning, shared learning platform, online education, teaching wood protection

1. INTRODUCTION

Today students wish to learn in a different way than in the past, taking advantage of modern communication technologies. Gone are the days where students are satisfied to sit in front of a professor and listen to words of wisdom all day long. Instead, students expect a well-designed content that they can study on-line whenever and wherever they want and interact with the professor in a more direct question and answer type scenario. The higher education sector is gradually adopting more flexible, individualised teaching methods.

In addition, higher education in wood science across Europe is often faced with administrative cut-backs on budgets, which tend to affect smaller departments like forestry and wood science. In some cases, institutes have difficulties to attract sufficient numbers of students to their wood science and technology courses. Furthermore, forestry and wood science courses are multidisciplinary and wide ranging. Research groups at universities need to develop their own scientific focus and profile. These aspects make it challenging for departments to cover all the

disciplines that make up wood science and, certainly, they cannot cover the wide range of topics in all peripheral areas. It is also anticipated that unless something changes, the number wood science departments in Europe will further decrease owing to this restructuration.

To adapt to this situation and make wood science departments fit for the future, modern information technologies offer great opportunities. What smaller departments need is access to a large online library of teaching modules on specific wood science topics that they can incorporate into their existing courses, to complete and upgrade their educational programmes. This will also offer more flexibility to students, who will be able to choose from a larger range of courses, and can also increase the quality of courses due to access to specialist knowledge in the fields covered.

InnovaWood is a European network of currently more than 50 member organisations in 27 countries. The members include leading research and technology institutes (RTOs), universities and vocational education and training (VET) centres all along the value chain from forestry and wood processing to construction, furniture and biochemicals. InnovaWood represents a common voice for promoting research and innovation about wood, one of Europe's mostly underdeveloped, important renewable raw materials, in line with the major policies of the European Union.

In 2017, several member institutes came together to launch under the umbrella of InnovaWood the Module Bank initiative. Collectively, the institutes have a broad range of existing courses and teaching modules in various wood science and technology topics and they also have the skills and resources to create and run such modules. With appropriate effort, these can be developed into a series of standalone online modules. As current information technologies and infrastructures become more and more widely accessible, the InnovaWood network can facilitate the building of a common platform dedicated for sharing these educational modules among its members.

2. THE CONCEPT OF A SHARED MODULE BANK IN WOOD SCIENCE

2.1 Participants

The main idea is simple. To become a participant of the Module Bank, each organisation has to commit to develop and contribute at least one module. In return it obtains as a participant the access to the whole series of modules that are offered collectively. The common platform is managed by InnovaWood. Institutes that want to participate in this initiative and gain access to the modules have to be members of InnovaWood. Besides the contribution of one module, the institutes agree to pay an annual fee for the administration of the Module Bank.

The institute signs an agreement that defines the legal basis for the Module Bank collaboration. It details the internal terms and conditions set by InnovaWood, i.e. the roles, rules and duties of a participant to contribute and gain access to the Module Bank. A *participant* is a member organisation of the InnovaWood network. A *beneficiary* is a participant that has obtained access to a module provided by another participant for the purpose of its own educational programmes.

The Module Bank is set up as a centralised Moodle platform, which ensures flexible sharing of modules among the participants, and controls the specific access rights of individual persons (e.g. authors, tutors, users) to the modules.

2.2 Definition of a module

One module shall consist of one *Master of Science* (MSc) level course equivalent to 3 ECTS credits (European Credit Transfer and Accumulation System). This corresponds typically to 60 to 90 hours of study for the student, with variations according to countries. It has to be ensured that the

modules are developed as complementary and shareable courses among universities and higher education schools.

Each module is a *stand-alone course*. It comprises a complete set of online accessible material that allows the beneficiaries to offer the module as a full course within their own study programmes. The tutoring and assessment are the responsibility of the beneficiary (see further details under 2.4). English is the common language (other languages can optionally be included as subtitles).

Modules can include various forms of content, as the author sees fit for attaining the learning objectives. Stand-alone online courses would in general include a main share as *on-line passive content* together with related offline study work. To enhance the interest and increase the chances of a student completing a module, it must also contain *on-line interactive* content; InnovaWood modules will have a minimum of 5% of interactive content. A module typically consists of a number of separate blocks, which are the smallest learning units. Each separate block should be fairly independent of the others and in general no longer than one hour. A block usually includes different forms of content, e.g. separate video sequences together with quiz questions, exercises, readings or other engaging content.

The participating organisations, or in exceptional cases the individual authors, retain ownership of their modules. The modules are created solely for educational purposes. All contents included in a module, which are not owned or licensed by the participant/author, have to be duly referenced according to good scientific practice. The participants create the modules within their means. In some institutions, authors can use inhouse support and professional equipment. Technical advice and training is also be provided from the InnovaWood eLearning expert team on demand. A bonus of this initiative is that lecturers have been able to share practice and learn together. There are many hundreds of good lecturers in forestry and wood science, but, very few with extensive experience in developing online modules.

At this stage of the initiative, only MSc level modules will be developed for the Module Bank. If these prove to be successful, it is possible at a later stage to extend the concept also to Bachelor of Science (BSc) level courses or practical training modules aimed at companies.

2.3 Quality assurance by peer review

A peer review process shall serve as principle approach to ensure a high scientific and educational quality of the content offered in the modules. Before a module can be published in the Module Bank, it will be assessed by the Steering Committee of the Module Bank. At least two competent persons will be nominated to carry out a review of the proposed module, to check that the module reflects the state of the art of the given scientific field and confirm that it fulfils the requirements and common objectives of the Module Bank.

Recommendations from peers shall help in a process of continuous improvement to enhance the quality of the modules more and more during the development. Peers, external experts, and at a later stage also student evaluations from previous years shall be considered as helpful feedback during the development of the Module Bank.

The modules also need to comply with minimum technical requirements and quality standards for digital content. These relate to technical specifications for the recording of video lectures, settings of equipment and used file formats. The peer review includes also recommendations from the team of e-Learning experts to ensure the required technical quality.

Specific recommendations for improvement are addressed to the author, if a module is not yet approved. Once a module has been approved, it will be opened in the Moodle platform. The standard duration for the approval of a module is at minimum two years. After this duration an update of the review is due. Participants are asked to ensure that the authors update and improve their modules on a regular basis, e.g. to include newest research findings.

2.4 Use of modules by beneficiaries and course assessment

InnovaWood is the host of the platform and manages the access rights to the modules. This includes an up-to-date centralised register about which modules are accessed by which beneficiary and are included in which study programme. When a module is incorporated by a beneficiary into a study programme, the beneficiary has to make sure that an appropriate citation of the authorship is provided, i.e. in their Learning Management System and any course material.

Beneficiaries have in principle free choice to use any part of a module, as they see fit for their own existing study programmes and curricula (e.g. out of a 3 ECTS module, an institution might decide to choose only the introductory parts to offer a 1 ECTS module to their students). It is also a possibility to select only specific sections (e.g. individual blocks or learning units) to complement another existing course. The modularity of the eLearning content allows a great deal of flexibility.

How a Module is incorporated into a course is the sole responsibility of the beneficiary that wishes to use the module. For obvious practical reasons, the author or the organisation who developed the module, cannot be responsible for the assessment of students from another university taking the module. It is unlikely that the online quizzes, calculations and other interactive content, that can be evaluated by computer, would satisfy an academic board at a university. Therefore, the beneficiary, i.e. the responsible tutor, has to organise how his students will be assessed in compliance with the requirements of the specific study programme.

To help, the modules include a range of suggestions and materials that should help support the assessment of students. This includes for example exercises/tests that can easily be marked, a list of typical exam questions or examples of project assignments. This part of content is only accessible to the tutor of a course and not to the students.

3. HOW TO DEVELOP AN ATTRACTIVE E-LEARNING MODULE

3.1 New learning methods and the e-Learning Expert Group

An important advantage of the Module Bank has already become clear during the initial development phase. The transition from a traditional classroom setup to a more individual, flexible teaching approach supported by digital tools is challenging; it needs a new mindset and didactical method acquired first of all by the teachers.

To convert a given typical lecture into an online e-Learning module is not as easy as it may seem at first glance: online content is much more condensed, needs to be well prepared and organised, and attractive, so that it sparks and facilitates the individual student's creative learning process. Because these methods are fairly new, most teachers in higher education (professors, research staff, lecturers) have little or no experience with e-Learning. This is why the first step is to familiarise the teachers with the context, possibilities and challenges of e-Learning methods.

For this purpose, it was decided to form an *e-Learning Expert Group*, whose task is to work out the technical and didactical questions of an e-Learning platform that can be shared between different institutions. A few organisations in the group are fortunate to have access to in-house e-

Learning professionals, who agreed to bring in their expertise to this initiative. In a series of regular online meetings, the team of experts worked out the definition what actually is a module, how it has to be structured, what requirements it needs to fulfil to be useful for other participants, and what are methods and tools to create attractive e-Learning content for such modules.

The exchange among teachers and e-Learning experts from different institutions turned out to be beneficial for all sides. Several points can be highlighted:

- For most teachers who are inexperienced with e-Learning, taking the first step is difficult. Through the support of the group, teachers learn how to design, plan and prepare a module in a coherent way and to consider rules and techniques that ensure a sufficient technical quality. They are introduced to new didactics and teaching methods of digital media and they learn how to best use specialised software and recording equipment.
- The e-Learning experts share their experiences about techniques and tools and discuss the best solutions for a given question that has been raised by the participants. A lot of tips and tricks are shared and specific problems can be addressed more quickly. For example, through the group, participants found out how different interactive elements offered in Moodle can be included into quizzes or tests, or how easily and practically the YouTube subtitle function can be used to enhance the learning experience of videos.
- In this way, modules are being reviewed by other participants as they are being developed and the author can receive immediate feedback on newly created pieces of content. The feedback from colleagues and non-experts is helpful to check if the structure of the learning units and the contents is easily understandable and interesting.
- The team has started to create an own ‘e-Learning Crash Course’ and put together a series of simple tutorials, where any participant can learn basic techniques. These include: screen-casting and video recording techniques, storyboard and module design, and e-Learning didactics. This will help new participants who intend to join the Module Bank to familiarise themselves with the concepts.
- All partners have confirmed that the discussions held at the monthly video-meetings provide very useful guidance and hands-on support for the development of the modules, but also helpful ideas for their own regular work.

3.2 Members of the initiative

The initiative started in 2017 within the InnovaWood network. Several member organisations stated their interest to join the initiative and develop the concept and the platform together.

Currently the following organisation are involved in the initiative (in alphabetical order):

- BFH: Bern University of Applied Sciences, Bern, Switzerland
- BOKU: University of Natural Resources and Life Sciences, Vienna, Austria
- TUD: Technological University of Dublin, Ireland
- ESB: École Supérieure du Bois, Nantes, France
- LUT: Luleå University of Technology, Sweden
- UG: University of Ghent Belgium
- UGOE: University of Göttingen, Germany
- UHH: University of Hamburg, Germany
- ULJ: University of Ljubljana, Slovenia
- UPR: University of Primorska / InnoRenew Center of Excellence, Slovenia

Each organisation drafted an outline of the module they intend to develop, including a brief description of the learning objectives and the indicative contents. The authors then started step by step to prepare their modules using video recording techniques and various software tools.

3.3 Examples of modules

The following modules are already well advanced and are expected to be completed soon:

- The Manufacture of Properties of Wood-based Panels, by ESB
- Wood-Based Panels: Adhesives and Emissions & Indoor Air Quality, by BFH
- Wood degradation and wood protection, by UGOE
- Wood and fiber quality, by BOKU
- Hygrothermal risk assessment of timber construction, by TUD

In addition, LTU has a number of existing modules, which it uses in current courses, that could be included in the InnovaWood Module Bank once the above modules are available.

Depending on the preferences and objectives of the author and the available resources at the organisation, the modules are using different formats of e-Learning. Each teacher has his/her own character and style of teaching, which is reflected in the module. This personal touch and rich variety of formats is a characteristic of the Module Bank shared platform, and makes the offered content lively and interesting to watch. The video recordings for example vary between self-recorded screencasts to semi-professional video productions (cf. Figures 1-5). The modules also differ in the way they are structured into learning units of different length, or how they include visuals, further study materials or interactive elements - just the same way as classical courses at a university can be diverse.

The main important point here, however, is that each author who presents a module is an acknowledged scientist and can build on a long experience as teacher. Through the Module Bank, he/she delivers high quality teaching content in his/her field of professional expertise, which becomes more widely accessible to students from other institutions through the digital format of an online module. The peer review from other colleagues helps the author to enhance the content and makes it more relevant for a wider audience of students in different countries.

Figure 1: Example of a screencast recorded presentation.
Dr. Mark Irlé from ESB introducing his module on wood-based panels.

Figure 2: Example of a screencast recorded presentation. Prof. Rupert Wimmer from BOKU explaining basics of wood and fiber quality.

Figure 3: Example of a studio-recorded lecture. Dr. Christian Brischke from University of Göttingen explaining classification methods for the durability of wood.

Figure 4: Example of a studio-recorded lecture. Prof. Andreja Kutnar of the InnoRenew CoE as guest lecturer at the University of Göttingen, introducing the research field of wood modification.

Figure 5: Example of a studio recording with full post production. Dr. Frédéric Pichelin of BFH introducing basics of adhesives in wood-based panels.

4. ADDED VALUE OF ONLINE TEACHING MODULES

The first main benefit of the Module Bank for university departments and technical schools is that they obtain a *cost-effective solution* to expand their study programmes. By contributing one module, they obtain access to a whole series of modules provided by other higher education institutions across Europe. It is true that building a complete MSc-level module equivalent to 3 ECTS requires a considerable effort and time from the professor or researcher who is the main author. But the cost should be seen as a good investment, because the amount of learning content that the institution obtains ‘almost for free’ in return is many times higher. Furthermore, the

Module Bank facilitates this transition from traditional lecture material to online modules by offering the participants a set of useful e-Learning training material and hands-on support from the e-Learning experts group.

The e-Learning environment gives students a *greater flexibility* to organise their studies as they wish. Conventional classroom lectures with a rigid time plan often collide with a student's other obligations (e.g. family, a job or other university events). An online module on the other hand can be studied anywhere and anytime, when it is most suitable for the student's own agenda. It is also easier to adapt his/her own speed to completing a course.

The flexibility of an online course also provides benefits to the own staff of an organisation. Although a lecturer will have to invest a lot of time to develop the module there will be returns in the future. A professor/teacher can use the module in a blended learning approach for his/her own students. He/she will be able to significantly reduce time for the preparation of lectures and giving the lectures because they will exist already. They can use their time with students via interactive tutoring of small groups or individual young researchers, i.e. acting as a 'coach' helping students to understand what they have studied. He/she will gain much more flexibility to develop his/her own research work, e.g. for international travels in research projects or other faculty commitments. Also the impact of sick leaves can be reduced. The option of blended learning gives a faculty much more possibilities to react spontaneously to unforeseeable situations.

The second main benefit for the students of a participating organisation in the Module Bank is that they obtain a *greater choice of course topics offered* within a study programme. The online modules can complement existing study programmes with topics or research fields in which the internal staff lack expertise. Moreover, these modules are provided by leading experts in their field. The modules thus can enhance also the quality of a course, adding teaching material with state-of-the-art research findings. This can help to raise the reputation and attractiveness of a study programme for the students. The goal of the Module Bank is to provide easy access to the knowledge of the best experts in a certain field.

As far as InnovaWood is concerned, the most important benefit of the Module Bank is that it fosters *international collaboration* in wood research and higher education with minimal effort. The online platform offers interesting new lectures and introduces senior professors and researchers from other universities to the students of a programme - in a way similar to a visiting professor or a lecturer from abroad, or similar to a foreign semester or a short term visit of a student to another country. Of course online modules can never replace the real experience of mobility, but they do for sure broaden the horizon of students, in a way that the local university cannot achieve on its own.

The Module Bank offers the opportunity to approach a course topic or research field from a wider, more *international perspective*. Students are introduced to topics by experienced researchers who have many different backgrounds and work in different country/regional contexts. Many authors are quite resourceful, as they are also active in European projects. The underlying peer review approach of the modules also ensures that the contents are relevant to various national contexts. This means that online modules consisting of many building blocks can also offer a broader content of more locally relevant or specific phenomena (for example, in the field of wood protection, termites play a very minor role in Nordic countries, but are regarded as one of the most important infestation organisms worldwide). In this sense online modules can widen the thematic scope of more traditional lectures focussed only on a national context.

Flexible online modules enriched with international contents may also be seen as a good first introduction for MSc students and young researchers to prepare for an international visit and/or get involved in collaborative research with research organisations in other countries. Partners of the Module Bank may also help establish contacts for students who wish to engage in exchange programmes and spend some time of their studies abroad.

On the other hand, for students who cannot go abroad for social or economic reasons, the online modules can be an opportunity to access lecture material of other universities without having the need for mobility. This can also become key advantage for a third target group: international students. A series of online modules could be packaged into a specific course for students from foreign countries, allowing them to take preparatory courses before their first visit to their host university, or continuing their studies from home once they have returned. In this sense the Module Bank can hold great benefits for the increase of international outreach of a university programme outside Europe.

5. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

Members of the InnovaWood network have jointly started the Module Bank initiative to develop an online platform for sharing complete sets of course materials (standalone modules) useful for blended learning. The platform shall benefit the participating university departments and schools in the modernisation of their higher education programmes towards more flexible e-Learning environments. The Module Bank shall facilitate sharing of high quality teaching content (MSc-level) between partner institutions, to complement their existing study programmes and offer a wider range of courses at efficient cost. The quality of teaching can be enhanced, not only on a professional level but also by adding easy to access international expertise and excellence. It is also expected that the international network behind the Module Bank will facilitate more mobility and exchange between institutions. Although the initial creation of an online module requires more time and effort than a conventional lecture, a return of investment will be achieved very quickly.

Already at this early stage, the synergies and benefits of the Module Bank collaboration became evident. The participating organisations have engaged in a regular exchange to jointly build the modules, to learn from each other's expertise and to use feedback from peers especially in the initial development phase. This has led to immediate improvements, as teachers are able to minimise making typical beginners' mistakes and it will help ensure the high quality of the final modules.

Several first modules will soon be ready in the InnovaWood Module Bank. Once the first set of modules is complete and approved, the Module Bank will be launched officially as a service provided by the EU network to its members. This is currently foreseen for September 2019. Further members of InnovaWood as well as other universities have already expressed an interest in the Module Bank. The aim of InnovaWood and its partners is to grow the initiative during the coming years: the more members will be committed to the initiative, the higher will be the synergies and benefits for all participating organisations.

The InnovaWood Module Bank has the potential to make a significant contribution to more exchange and collaboration in wood science, research and training in Europe. Interested parties who wish to learn more about the Module Bank initiative are invited to directly contact one of the authors of this paper.